

Herbarium of the University of Coimbra Data Management Plan

Version 1

Description

The digitisation of all the processes creating digital data that need to be organised and maintained in a structured way. This DMP intends to set the principles to manage the digital information of the Herbarium of the University of Coimbra

Funder

n.a.

Grant

n.a.

Researchers

Joaquim Santos (orcid:0000-0002-2160-4968)

Organizations

University of Coimbra

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Herbarium of the University of Coimbra Data Management Plan](#)

Description:

The digitisation of all the processes creating digital data that need to be organised and maintained in a structured way. This DMP intends to set the principles to manage the digital information of the Herbarium of the University of Coimbra

Researchers:

[Joaquim Santos \(orcid:0000-0002-2160-4968\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Coimbra](#)

Contact: [Joaquim Santos](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: n.a.

Grants: n.a.

Project: n.a.

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[CMS Database \(Specify\)](#)

Instance of Specify database, managed through the built-in interface, or other interactions. SPECIFY Software is a Collections Management System and is the main tool used in the herbarium to manage the collection (herbarium specimen records, loans, etc.).

Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: Dataset

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

mysql database

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

mysql

Creation of a record on the Specify CMS for each specimen of the collection. The main values will be filled in manually by members of the staff, or automatically by script processes based on the images of the specimens (values provided by the person acquiring images of the specimens). Other data will be filled in by staff or volunteers in-house, or by volunteers using the online crowdsourcing tool Explorator.

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

0 - 10 GB

This dataset does not store any images, only text

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

no documentation, besides the metadata

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

GBIF Metadata Profile

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

GBIF Metadata Profile

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

eng

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

Every day a copy of the database will be stored in a separate disk

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Full backup

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Daily

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Not applicable (no sensitive data)

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

Yes

4.1.2 How will compliance with legislation and (institutional) regulation on personal data be ensured?

Every Personal data stored should follow European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

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University of Coimbra

The owner of the data is the University of Coimbra, and the responsible for it is the Collection Manager in charge of Data

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

Other (please specify)

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as archived in repository

Relevant data for researchers will become available on the Herbarium Data Portal (<https://coicatalogue.uc.pt>), and on GBIF, by publishing it using the IPT of the GBIF Portugal node

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

Portugal IPT - GBIF Portugal

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

None of the above

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

url

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

Data is available using an Internet Browser in the context of the Herbarium Data Portal (<https://coicatalogue.uc.pt>), and GBIF

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

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University of Coimbra

data capture; metadata production; data quality; storage and backup; data archiving; data sharing.

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

Automatic mechanisms will be put in place to update the data automatically in repositories, but staff will guarantee that the data is shared when needed.

Specimen images

Images captured from specimens using an inverted flatbed scanner (HerbScan) or captured with a digital camera

Template: [FCT - Template in English](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

images

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

tif, jpg

The images are produced in-house and fed into a pipeline where they are replicated, converted and stored.

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

With about 75.000 original images, the space occupied is ca. 3TB. For a total of 800.000 specimens the data storage can grow to more than 30 TB or more, depending on the quality of the images captured.

2.1 Documentation

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no documentation, besides the metadata

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

A metadata file with the description of each individual image is created daily. The standard used is the Audiovisual Core (AC), previously known as Audubon Core, maintained by the Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Audiovisual Core (AC) [previously known as Audubon Core]

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

eng

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

Yes

The data is mirrored to other storage units on-site and also to remote storage.

3.1.4 Please describe the type of backup.

Mirror backup

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.5 Please describe the frequency of backup.

Daily

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Not applicable (no sensitive data)

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

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5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as archived in repository

Images become available on the Herbarium Data Portal (<https://coicatalogue.uc.pt>), and on GBIF, by publishing it using the IPT of the GBIF Portugal node

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None of the above

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Yes

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